

Search for Potential Antitumour Compounds. Part II. Synthesis of Some Arybiguanide Mustards

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Several nitrogen mustard derivatives of arylbiguanides have been prepared with a view to testing their antitumour activity.

In spite of the wide interest in derivatives of bis-(2-chloroethyl)amine (nitrogen mustard) as potential antitumour agents, no report of *NN*-bis-(2-chloroethyl)biguanides has appeared in the literature. Although one would not expect biguanides of type (I) to exhibit alkylating action as such, it is likely that these may be transformed in the body to an active mustard. It is well known that the biguanides are cyclised to triazine and dihydrotriazine¹ derivative *in situ* as a result of their interaction with acids and ketones inside the body. A number of cyclic triazine derivatives, like triethylene melamine (TEM) etc. and dihydrotriazines²⁻³, have also been found to exhibit antineoplastic activity. Based on these observations, several *N*¹-aryl-*N*⁵*N*⁵-bis-(2-chloroethyl)biguanides of type (I) have been synthesised. The biguanides were synthesised by the following methods.

(a). By refluxing equimolecular quantities of the appropriate aryldicyandiamide and diethanolamine hydrochloride in anhydrous ethanol and subsequently treating the resulting *N*¹-aryl-*N*⁵*N*⁵-bis-(2-hydroxyethyl)biguanide (II) with thionyl chloride.

The compound (I) could not be obtained directly from the aryldicyandiamide and bis-(2-chloroethyl)amine hydrochloride by refluxing in anhydrous ethanol.

1. Crowther and Levi, *Brit. J. Pharmacol.*, 1953, **8**, 93.
2. Farber *et al.*, *Amer. J. Pathol.*, 1952, **28**, 559.
3. Føber *et al.*, *Proc. Amer. Assoc. Cancer Res.*, 1953, **1**, 15.

(b). From arylguanidine and *N*-cyano-bis-(2-chloroethyl)amine (III) by the method of Ainley *et al.*⁴

(c). By condensation of the appropriate arylamine hydrochloride and *N'**N'*-bis-(2-hydroxyethyl)dicyandiamide (IV) and subsequently treating the bis (2-hydroxyethyl)-biguanide (II) with thionyl chloride.

Compound (IV) was prepared by two different methods. The following steps are involved.

Replacement of the hydroxyl group of this compound (IV) by chlorine (by treating with thionyl chloride) provided the corresponding *N'**N'*-bis (2-chloroethyl)dicyandiamide (V). Attempts to synthesise arylbiguanide mustards (I) from this chloroethyl compound (V) by treating it with arylamine hydrochloride led to resinous products which were difficult to crystallise.

*EXPERIMENTAL

Substituted aryl dicyandiamides were prepared by the method of Curd and Rose⁵.

*N'**N'*-Bis-(2-hydroxyethyl)dicyandiamide (IV): *Method (a)*.—Ethylene oxide (0.3*M*), cooled below 0°, was added to dicyandiamide (0.1*M*) and the mixture heated in a sealed tube at 125° for 12 hr. The viscous mass obtained was distilled under reduced pressure. The fraction boiling at 110-12°/9 mm was collected; it solidified to a white crystalline mass on keeping over P₂O₅ for a few days; yield 30%, m.p. 82°. (Found: N, 32.4. C₆H₁₂O₂N₄ requires N, 32.6%).

*All melting points are uncorrected. Mixed melting points of identical compounds obtained by different methods did not show any depression.

4. Ainley *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 98,

5. *Ibid.*, 1946, 729.

Method (b).—Diethanolamine hydrochloride (0.1*M*), sodium dicyanamide (0.1*M*), and butanol (30 ml) were refluxed with stirring for 3 hr. The cooled suspension was filtered and evaporated. The residual syrup was fractionally distilled as in method (a) and the dicyandiamide (IV), boiling at 110-12°/9 mm, solidified on keeping over P₂O₅ for a few days; yield 70%, m.p. 81-82°.

N,N'-Bis-(2-chloroethyl)dicyandiamide (V): *Method (a).*—It was obtained similarly as in method (b) above from bis-(2-chloroethyl)amine hydrochloride (0.01*M*), sodium dicyanamide (0.01*M*), and butanol (15 ml). The residual syrup, obtained after evaporation of butanol, solidified on treatment with chloroform. The compound was crystallised from the same solvent in colorless prisms, yield 75%, m.p. 56°. (Found: N, 26.6. C₆H₁₀N₄Cl₂ requires N, 26.8%).

Method (b).—A mixture of *N,N'*-bis-(2-hydroxyethyl)dicyandiamide (0.01*M*) and thionyl chloride (0.03*M*) was kept at the room temperature for 6 hr. The excess of thionyl chloride was then removed under reduced pressure at 50-60°. The residual syrup solidified on treatment with chloroform. The compound was purified by repeated crystallisation from the same solvent; yield 20%, m.p. 56°.

N,N'-Bis-(2-hydroxyethyl)biguanide.—Diethanolamine (0.05*M*) and dicyandiamide (0.05*M*) were boiled under reflux in aqueous solution (70 ml water) for 1 hr. Copper sulphate solution (40%) was then added to this reaction mixture in small portions till the copper hydroxide, precipitated from the previous addition, dissolved to form a blue-violet solution. The mixture was then filtered and cooled in ice. The rose-coloured crystals of copper complex separating was filtered, suspended in water (100 ml), and into this H₂S was passed till saturation. Precipitated copper sulphide was filtered and the filtrate concentrated in vacuum after addition of H₂SO₄ (conc., 8 ml). The concentrated solution was then treated with acetone when white crystalline diethanolbiguanide sulphate separated; yield 55%, m.p. 227°. (Found: N, 24.0. C₆H₁₇O₆N₅S requires N, 24.4%).

The free base was obtained from its sulphate by dissolving it in anhydrous ethanol and passing dry ammonia gas into it. The precipitated ammonium sulphate was filtered and the free base was obtained as a thick syrup after evaporation of the solvent.

N,N'-Bis-(2-chloroethyl)biguanide: *Method (a).*—Bis-(2-chloroethyl)amine hydrochloride (0.01*M*), dicyandiamide (0.01*M*), and anhydrous ethanol (20 ml) were refluxed for 4 hr. The reaction mixture was kept overnight when white colorless needles of the hydrochloride separated. These were filtered and recrystallised from anhydrous ethanol; yield 40%, m.p. 157° (decomp.). (Found: N, 26.5. C₆H₁₄N₅Cl₃ requires N, 26.7%).

Method (b).—A mixture of *N,N'*-bis-(2-hydroxyethyl)biguanide (0.01*M*) and thionyl chloride (0.03*M*) was kept at the room temperature for 6 hr. Anhydrous ether was then added to this mixture, shaken well, and filtered. The process was repeated thrice. The solid thus obtained was recrystallised from anhydrous ethanol; yield 40%, m.p. 156-57° (decomp.).

N-Cyano-bis-(2-chloroethyl)amine (III).—To a suspension of bis-(2-chloroethyl)amine hydrochloride (0.05*M*) in benzene (200 ml) were added CNBr (0.05*M*) and NaOH (0.1*M*) (as 35% aq. soln.) stepwise and alternately. The mixture was stirred well during the

addition and stirred further for 2 hr. The benzene layer was then separated, dried, and evaporated to leave the *N*-cyano-bis-(chloroethyl)amine as an oil; b.p. 142°/9 mm, yield 75%. (Found: N, 16.4. $C_5H_8N_2Cl_2$ requires N, 16.7%).

*N*¹-Phenyl-*N*⁵*N*⁵-bis-(2-hydroxyethyl)biguanide (II: R=H): *Method (a)*.—A solution of *N*¹*N*⁵-bis-(2-hydroxyethyl)dicyandiamide (0.01*M*) and aniline hydrochloride (0.01*M*) in anhydrous ethanol (10 ml) was refluxed for 4 hr. White needles of the hydrochloride separated on cooling; yield 50%, m.p. 163°. (Found: N, 23.1. $C_{12}H_{20}O_2N_5Cl$ requires N, 23.3%).

Method (b).—Phenyldicyandiamide (0.01*M*), diethanolamine hydrochloride (0.01*M*), and anhydrous ethanol (10 ml) were refluxed for 4 hr. The hydrochloride separated as white needles on cooling; yield 55%, m.p. 163°.

The yields, m.p., and analyses of other biguanides prepared by the above methods are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

*N*¹-Aryl-*N*⁵*N*⁵-bis-(2-hydroxyethyl)biguanide hydrochlorides (II).

R.	Method.	%Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
4-Methyl	(a)	47	217°	$C_{13}H_{22}O_2N_5Cl$	21.9	22.2
"	(b)	50	217°	$C_{13}H_{22}O_2N_5Cl$	22.1	22.2
4-Ethyl	(a)	60	233°	$C_{14}H_{24}O_2N_5Cl$	21.2	21.3
"	(b)	51	234°	$C_{14}H_{24}O_2N_5Cl$	21.1	21.3
4-Methoxy	(a)	40	110°	$C_{13}H_{22}O_3N_5Cl$	20.6	20.7
"	(b)	67	111°	$C_{13}H_{22}O_3N_5Cl$	20.9	20.7
4-Ethoxy	(a)	49	129°	$C_{14}H_{24}O_3N_5Cl$	20.1	20.3
"	(b)	72	129°	$C_{14}H_{24}O_3N_5Cl$	20.1	20.3
4-Hydroxy	(a)	63	176°	$C_{12}H_{20}O_3N_5Cl$	21.9	22.1
4-Carboxy	(a)	48	> 250°	$C_{13}H_{20}O_4N_5Cl$	20.0	20.3
4-Sulphonyl	(a)	60	> 250	$C_{12}H_{20}O_5N_5ClS$	17.8	17.6
4-Acetamino	(a)	50	> 250°	$C_{14}H_{22}O_3N_6Cl$	23.1	23.5
4-Nitro	(a)	50	> 250°	$C_{12}H_{18}O_4N_6Cl$	24.2	24.3
4-Chloro	(a)	72	227°	$C_{12}H_{18}O_2N_5Cl_2$	20.6	20.8
4-Bromo	(a)	78	215°	$C_{12}H_{19}O_2N_5BrCl$	18.0	18.4

*N*¹-Phenyl-*N*⁵*N*⁵-bis-(2-chloroethyl)biguanide (I: R = H): *Method (a)*.—The *N*¹-phenyl-*N*⁵*N*⁵-bis-(2-hydroxyethyl)biguanide (0.01*M*) was treated with thionyl chloride (0.03*M*) and the mixture kept at 50-60° for 1 hr. Excess of thionyl chloride was removed under reduced pressure. The mustard derivative, so obtained, was recrystallised from anhydrous ethanol; yield 70%, m.p. 187°. (Found: N, 20.6. $C_{12}H_{18}N_5Cl_2$ requires N, 20.70%).

Method (b).—*N*-Phenylguanidine hydrochloride (0.01*M*) and *N*-cyano-bis-(2-chloroethyl)amine were refluxed in butanol (25 ml) for 6 hr. The mixture was then concentrated to half its volume and HCl gas was passed when crystals of the hydrochloride of the base (I)

separated on cooling; yield 37%, m.p. 188°. (Found: N, 20.6. $C_{12}H_{18}N_3Cl_3$ requires N, 20.7%). The yields, m.p., and analyses of other biguanides, prepared by the above methods, are reported in Table II.

TABLE II

*N*¹-Aryl-*N*⁵*N*⁵-bis-(2-chloroethyl)biguanide hydrochloride (I)

R.	Method.	% Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
4-Methyl	(a)	62	173°	$C_{13}H_{20}N_3Cl_3$	20.0	19.9
4-Ethyl	(a)	76	201°	$C_{14}H_{22}N_3Cl_3$	18.7	19.1
4-Methoxy	(a)	67	98°	$C_{13}H_{20}ON_3Cl_3$	18.7	19.0
4-Ethoxy	(a)	89	76°	$C_{14}H_{22}ON_3Cl_3$	18.1	18.3
4-Hydroxy	(a)	52	219°	$C_{12}H_{18}ON_3Cl_3$	19.5	19.8
4-Carboxy	(a)	47	> 250°	$C_{13}H_{15}O_2N_3Cl_3$	18.5	18.3
4-Sulphonyl	(a)	49	> 250°	$C_{14}H_{18}O_3N_3Cl_3S$	16.4	16.3
4-Acetamino	(a)	76	207°	$C_{14}H_{21}ON_6Cl_3$	21.2	21.3
4-Nitro	(a)	78	> 250°	$C_{12}H_{17}O_2N_6Cl_3$	22.0	22.0
4-Nitro	(b)	26	> 250°	$C_{12}H_{17}O_2N_6Cl_3$	21.7	22.0
4-Chloro	(a)	82	> 250°	$C_{12}H_{17}N_3Cl_4$	18.6	18.8
4-Chloro	(b)	35	> 250°	$C_{12}H_{17}N_3Cl_4$	19.0	18.8
4-Bromo	(a)	90	248°	$C_{12}H_{17}N_3Cl_3Br$	17.0	16.8

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